
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DOMESTIC ENERGY USE IN NIGERIA - A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria is naturally blessed with abundant sources of renewable and non-renewable energy. The development, exploitation and utilisation of these energy sources have been largely skewed in favour of hydro power and crude oil, leaving the other sources either untouched or poorly harnessed. Also the impact of the exploitation of both energy sources on the environment has been largely ignored over the years. In recent years, solar PV installations for street lighting, water pumping, vaccine refrigerators and powering of remote communities (islanding) by use of photovoltaic panels is increasing in some parts of Nigeria. Researches on domestic energy use in different States in Nigeria show that fuelwood is predominantly used in the rural areas while the urban areas mostly use kerosene stove, local gas cooker, local electric cooker, sawdust stove, charcoal stove and firewood as cooking fuels. This paper present a comprehensive review of the literature of domestic energy consumption in Nigeria from desk study of open literature survey approach. The work further analysed the environmental, health and economic implications of the current domestic energy use in Nigeria and also proffers possible solutions.

KEYWORDS: domestic energy use, fuelwood, households, environment.

Received for Publication: 23/06/13

Accepted for Publication: 01/10/13

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INTRODUCTION

Domestic energy use and economic growth are interrelated. Studies done by Akinlo (Akinlo, 2008) using the ARDL (autoregressive distributed lags) approach indicates that energy consumption is cointegrated with economic growth. Domestic energy use generally refers to the amount of energy used in a household. This depends on a lot of factors such as the standard of living of the country, climate, the type of residence, age of the occupants, and literacy level (Nnaji 2012, Abayomi, 2012, Okoro and Madueme, 2004, Olatinwo and Adewumi, 2012). Nigeria has abundant sources of renewable and non-renewable energy. Despite this, the national energy supply is largely dependent on fossil fuels and firewood for their domestic energy needs. Fossil fuels constitute 94% of exports from Nigeria in 2006 with only a small fraction of this available for domestic use and about 40% of households connected to the national electricity grid (Akpu, 2012). Proliferation of gasoline generators is common in all parts of Nigeria due to the epileptic nature of power supply from the national grid. This is further highlighted by the works of different researchers in the literature (Olawale et. al. 2012, Abayomi, 2012, Anthony and Emodi, 2012, Babanyara and Saleh, 2010). It has been reported that over 90% businesses and companies in Nigeria have private generators leading to high production cost of locally produced materials (Omokaro, 2008). This will also lead to environmental pollution and increased greenhouse gases due to CO₂ (carbon (iv) oxide) and CO (carbon (ii) oxide) emission.

It is glaringly clear that most of our traditional energy sources such as fossil fuels, coal and natural gas will inevitably run out in the near future, possibly leading to a global demand for a new source of power. At present, a greater percentage of the energy needs in Nigeria is supplied by the oil sector. Some analysts have predicted a total or near collapse of world oil production in 2050 (Campbell, 1996, 2000, Campbell and Laherrère, 1998). The energy consumption mix in Nigeria is dominated by fuel wood (50.45%), petroleum products (41.28%) and hydro electricity (8%) while biomass, solar, wind geothermal, coal and nuclear sources are largely ignored (Omokaro, 2008). In the rural areas, the volume of energy used, and type of energy depends on the population size, lifestyle, and economic status of the household but in urban areas, population density, economic status and

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urbanisation plays a key role. Reports have shown that in some urban areas, there is an increase in the use of kerosene among the middle and low income group (Chikaire et. al., 2011, Famuyide et. al., 2011, Anthony and Ojochenemi 2012, Adegbemi et. al. 2013). However high cost, and constant artificial scarcity of kerosene in most parts of Nigeria has pushed many household to use of charcoal. This is evident in the recent increase in pump price of petroleum product in early 2012 (Abd'razack et. al. 2012, Oyekale et. al. 2012).

Cooking, laundry and heating constitutes the bulk of house hold energy use in most developing countries especially among poor households. The absolute poverty rate of Nigeria was 61.9% by 2011 (Yemi, 2012) implying that the major domestic energy consumption is predominantly fuel wood because it is cheap and easily available. Report in the literature (Elijah, 2012) indicate that charcoal, wood biomass accounts for 31% and 50% of cooking energy sources for urban and rural areas in Nigeria, thus making it to be the dominant cooking fuel source. The study also show that 42% and 33% of urban and rural dwellers respectively use kerosene while only 10% of the urban dwellers use liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) for cooking, and a further 4% of the rural dwellers use LPG as cooking fuels (Elijah, 2012). Detailed statistics of domestic energy use and sustainability constitute important framework for assessing the impact of changes in environmental policy, structure and regulation of energy companies, public awareness of environmental issues, energy saving initiatives and energy sustainability.

Current Energy Status in Nigeria

Research has shown that the current Nation's available electricity generating capacity is about 3,920MW with per capita power capacity of 28.57 Watts (Ibidapo-Obe and Ajibola, 2011). The availability of power in Nigeria is reported to vary between 27% to 60% of installed capacity, while transmission and distribution losses constitute up to 28% of the electricity generated (Omokaro, 2008). It has been reported that successive Nigeria governments do concentrate electricity supply in the urban areas (Abayomi 2012, Nnaji 2012, Eric 1994, Audu 2013, Osueke and Ezeugwu, 2011). A scenario that leaves the rural populace with no other choice than fuelwood. Some reasonable percentage rely on biomass, charcoal, coal, sawdust and bio-ethanol as indicated in the works of different research groups in the literature for their domestic energy needs (Elijah, 2012, Eric, 1994, Babanyara and Saleh, 2010, Shittu, 2004). The current power generating capacity in Nigeria is about 4212.5 MW (Nnaji, 2012) hence for Nigeria to meet her energy needs; it requires a power generating capacity of 140,000 MW which will translate to per capital power capacity of approximately 1000 MW going by the 140,431,790 people of the 2006 census figure (NBS, 2010). Uzoma et. al. (2012) indicated that only about 20% of the over 10,000MW total exploitable large-scale hydropower potential in Nigeria, capable of producing 36,000GWh of electricity annually had been developed as at 2001 while the estimate of exploitable small-scale hydropower potential is at 734MW. About 40, 000MW of power is needed by the year 2020 if the Federal Government of Nigeria will meet her aim on "Vision 20-20-20", thus requiring extensive generation, transmission and distribution infrastructure with up to 100 billion US dollars in 10 years with generation at \$3.5billion/year for the next 8 years (Nnaji 2012, Yemi 2013).

Current Energy Consumption Pattern in Nigeria

Energy consumption pattern in Nigeria can be broadly grouped into urban and rural spheres, with urban sub-group to include: industry, transport, commercial, household and agricultural sectors. It is a common knowledge that there are disparities in the energy consumed by urban households and rural households, between high and low income group; within a region, country and among different countries. Table 1 gives the various contributions of different research groups in the literature on the relationship between energy consumption and economic growth in Nigeria. Another contributing factor to energy consumption in Nigeria is urbanisation. It has been reported that urbanisation influences demand for cheaper energy in Nigeria because of high level of poverty (Yemi, 2012). The use and differences in energy consumption also depends on the level of urbanisation, economic development and lifestyle (Dzioubinski and Chipman, 1999). As reflected in the work of Abd'razack et. al. (2012), a direct relationship exists between energy consumption, poverty and environment. To this end, energy consumption pattern under; electricity, kerosene, fuelwood, charcoal and biomass are discussed.

Electricity

Increase in electricity tariff by subsequent government is almost a common phenomenon in Nigeria. Report by Abd'razack et. al. (2012) indicated that there is an increase from 2.30 N/KWhr to 11.75NKWhr between 2000 to 2012. Moreso, only a little percentage (urban areas) are connected to the national grid. This is clearly highlighted in the works of different authors (Sambo 2010, Abd'razack et. al. (2012), Abayomi 2012, Babanyara and Saleh 2010, Shittu et. al. 2004, Audu 2013). The problem of voltage fluctuation, power supply inconsistency, family size and attendant electric shock is another discouraging factor towards use of electricity (electric stoves) for cooking even in urban areas. This has pushed up the percentage of household that use other source of fuels for cooking as reflected in the works of (Taru et. al. 2011, Oyekale et. al. 2012, Nnaji. et al. 2012, Ojo and Chuffor, 2013). Recent work by Nwosu and Nnamdi (2013), indicated that unstable power supply in Nigeria generally affect national output negatively and consequently reduces her per capita income.

Table 1. Literature of energy consumption and economic growth in Nigeria.

Authors	Energy consumption and economic growth in Nigeria	Method	Variables considered	Observation
Dantama et. al., 2012	Investigated the period 1980-2010	Autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach to co-integration analysis	Economic growth (GDP), total energy consumption (TEC), petroleum, gas, electricity, coal	Long run relationship between economic growth and energy consumption variables exists
Odularu and Okonkwo, 2009	Investigated the period 1970-2005	Co-integration technique	Crude oil, electricity and coal	Positive relationship exist between energy consumption and economic growth
Orhewere and Machame, 2011	Investigated the period 1970-2005	Vector error correction based Granger causality test	Economic growth (GDP), total energy consumption (TEC), gas, electricity	Uni-directional and bi-directional causality
Olusegun, 2008	1970-2005	ARDL	oil, gas and electricity	Unidirectional casual relationship
Omotor, 2008	...	Hsiao's Granger causality version	coal, electricity and oil	...
Akpan and Akpan, 2012	Investigated the period 1970 to 2008	Multivariate Vector Error Correction (VECM)	...	...
Olaniyan, 2010	1970-2005 (5 West African countries including Nigeria)	Granger causality tests and cointegration analysis,	...	...

Kerosine

The high cost and unavailability of kerosene in the market is common in all parts of Nigeria. This also applies to the constant increase in price by successive governments and hoarding of this essential commodity for maximum selfish gain by wholesalers. It has been reported by various authors that increased use of fuelwood, charcoal and biomass as cooking fuels in Nigeria is wholly due to the high cost and scarcity of kerosene (Oyekale et. al. 2012, Nnaji et. al. 2012, Ojo and Chuffor 2013).

Fuelwood

Fuelwood provides the main source of domestic fuel for both the rural and urban dwellers especially in developing countries. It has been reported that half of the world's population depend on fuelwood for cooking and other domestic uses, with a daily per capita consumption of about 0.5kg to 1.00kg of dry biomass (Twindel and Wier, 1986). According to Williams (1998), fuelwood account for 86% of national energy consumption for rural households in Nigeria. Based on the International Energy Agency (IEA) report, EIA (2010), nearly 81 million people in the rural areas are not accessible to electricity in Nigeria and thus biomass, especially fuel wood accounts for over 80% of their total energy consumption for off-grid heating and cooking needs. Different authors (Eric 1994, Nnaji et. al. 2012, Taru et. al. 2011, Fawehinmi and Oyerinde, 2002, Abd'razack et. al. 2012, Ouedraogo 2006, Audu 2012, Madubansi and Shackleton 2007, Bukola 2012, Pundo and Fraser, 2006, Anthony and Emodi 2012) identified several indices that determine choice of energy for domestic use and mostly points to poverty amongst other factors as the major reason for overdependence of fuel wood by most households in Nigeria.

Charcoal

Charcoal is formed when wood is burnt. Charcoal is used for cooking, ironing, blacksmith, gunpowder, art and medicine, as filter, catalyst, adsorbent, and for cultural costume. However, production of charcoal requires that vegetation must be affected since trees have to be felled. Nigeria is endowed with abundant fuel wood from forestry. Use of charcoal for cooking is more common in urban areas. Report has shown that a sizeable percentage of low/middle income urban dwellers use charcoal to augment their domestic energy needs (Eric 1994, Olabiuisi 2011). Persistent/increased use of charcoal for cooking fuel will surely lead to increased desertification, loss of farmland to erosion and serious negative impact on the environment.

Biomass

Most developing countries use biomass energy for cooking. Broadly speaking, sources of biomass include wood, energy crops, agricultural residue, food waste and industrial wastes. Report from different research groups indicates that the potential of biomass energy in Nigeria is very high (Akinwande et. al. 2013, Lawali and Bubuche 2013, Edward and Paul, 2013). The advantages of biomass energy if used in a sustainable manner, forms a reasonable part of the carbon cycle through arboricultural management or coppicing. The use of biomass related materials for domestic energy use in Nigeria due to unavailability and high cost of modern energy services has been reported by various authors (Danshehu et. al. 1992, Bolaji 2005, Momoh and Soaga 1999, Akinbami et. al. 2001, Ladipo et. al., 2002, Onyekuru and Eboh 2011). Unsustainable use of biomass has antecedent problems hence harnessing biomass energy need to be done in a sustainable manner in order to reap its immense benefits.

Environmental Implications

Energy is one of the major fundamental requirements for economic growth and stability, thus availability of quality energy is an essential ingredient to economic, social and environmental development. Use of energy in a sustainable manner leads to sustainable development (i.e. generation and use of energy in such a way that it meet the energy needs of the present generation without posing a risk now or in the future) and safe environment. Report of the National Energy Commission (2008) and that of Fawehinmi and Oyerinde (2002) highlighted the impact of insufficient supply of energy on all aspects of development especially social, economic, environmental, and even quality of life of the populace. Over-dependence on the use of wood, charcoal, crop residues and untreated coal for cooking in developing countries has serious negative consequences on both people and environment. This is because fuelwood, charcoal, agricultural residues, animal dung and saw dust all produce high emissions of carbon monoxide, hydrocarbons and particulate matter which are agents of air pollution and global warming. Although energy is needed to improve life, generation and consumption of some forms of energy has resulted in pollution of land, atmosphere, vegetation and rivers hence energy sustainability must be encouraged.

Every State in Nigeria has some form of environmental issue, with some being unique or similar to every State. For instance, current report by Elom (2013), on healthcare solid waste management in Nigeria indicated that the environment is under threat due to indiscriminate dumping of healthcare solid waste and poor management practices. Nwoke (2013) noted that the rate of waste generation in some State is alarming and these waste are poorly managed, hence leading to environmental problems. It has been reported that a total of 2,000 reports of

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oil spillages were recorded with the discharge of two million barrels of oil into the environment between 1976 to 1988 (Ikporukpo, 1988). Unchecked urbanisation in most States in Nigeria also add its quota on environmental degradation. Most towns in Nigeria are increasingly threatened by air and water pollution, and poor solid wastes disposal/management while the rural areas are plagued by soil erosion, deforestation, and bush burning (Babalola 2010, NEST, 1991, Anierobi and Efobi, 2013).

The report of NNPC (2010) indicated that gas flaring accounts for up to 63% of the total production. This translates to 63% of the environment being polluted especially in the oil producing regions. Report by Dike (1995) noted that over 2million tonnes of soil are lost annually in south-central Nigeria while Babanyara and Saleh, (2010) reported that an average of 409,700 hectares of forest, equal to an average annual deforestation rate of 2.38% was lost between 1990 and 2000, and 35.7% of the forest cover, or around 6,145,000 hectares was lost between 2000-2005 in Nigeria. In most developing countries, people give little priority on the need to preserve their environment because of poverty, illiteracy and lack of awareness on the short and long-term negative consequences.

Health Implications

The commonly used fuelwood has a lot of health risk (respiratory, pulmonary and carcinogenic) associated with their regular usage. Different research groups (Nigeria Energy Report 2005, Omaka et. al. 2013, Bukola 2012, Nnaji et. al. 2010) have reported on the negative consequences of using fuelwood on the health of households. The household sector is the largest single energy consumer and cooking constitutes the dominant energy needs in most developing countries. Studies done by Bukola (2012) conclude that indoor air pollution associated with the use of biomass energy is directly responsible for deaths more than malaria, almost as many as tuberculosis and almost half as many as HIV/AIDS. It has been reported that in most developing countries, the household sector accounts for more than 90% of total energy consumption (MacCarthy 2010). With the household sector accounting for 90% of the total energy consumption in developing countries (MacCarthy 2010, World Bank 2006, WHO, 2007), the health implication on household occupants due to domestic energy consumption is really significant.

Economic Implications

Each source of domestic energy use has its economic implications based on its impact on the user and on the environment with the exception of few sources such as solar energy. It has been established that firewood consumption has serious negative consequences for the environment (air pollution), climate (global warming), deforestation, loss of farmland, and health-related issues. Artificial scarcity of crude oil products used as domestic energy, oil spillage, erratic power supply and non-existence of power in most rural areas in Nigeria has persistently continued to create untold hardships on many. Illiteracy and unsustainable use of energy in Nigeria also add some economic burden to the users and to the Government. For instance, it has been reported that turning lights off when not in use would save a gigantic sum of £55m and 375000 tons of carbon (iv) oxide (The Cambridge-MIT Project, 2005), thus preserving the environment and reducing energy cost simultaneously. The attitude of switching lights off when not needed is hardly practiced in most part of Nigeria due to lack of awareness or illiteracy.

The way forward

The dominant source of energy for domestic use in Nigeria has been shown to be fuelwood based on the analysis from literature so far. The Nigeria's over-dependence on oil for energy has also been stressed by different authors (Nnaji et. al., 2010, Muhiddin et. al., 2011). The author strongly suggests that domestic energy use could be improved by:

- ❖ Use of more environmentally friendly fuelwood (Omaka et al., 2013).
- ❖ Use of improved cooking stoves (Eric, 1994).
- ❖ Use of bio-ethanol sources (Elijah, 2012).
- ❖ Poverty. Government at all levels should do more in eradicating poverty in Nigeria. This will contribute immensely in reducing the sole dependence on fuelwood by most households.
- ❖ Illiteracy. It is shocking and painful that most State Governments in Nigeria have stopped building new public secondary schools, old ones are poorly equipped and public education sector grossly ignored at all Government levels (federal, state and local).

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Government at all levels should do more in practice in reducing the rate of illiteracy in Nigeria. This will quicken the understanding of any awareness programme on sustainable use of energy, practice of such energy use and overall improvement in the quality of life of Nigerian citizens.

- ❖ Government should open other sources of energy that are naturally abundant in Nigeria.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a literature survey of domestic energy use in Nigeria has been undertaken and it indicated that fuelwood constitute the major source of cooking fuel of most households. The study showed that the current approaches to domestic energy use are not sustainable and will, in fact, make energy a barrier to socio-economic development in view of the environmental, health and economic implications of using fuelwood or biomass related materials. The high cost of kerosene, its unavailability, constant increase of pump prices by successive Governments, and erratic power supply to areas lucky to be connected to the national grid has made Nigeria a dumping ground for all kinds of fuel generator and also forced most households to depend on fuelwood as the only source of cooking fuel. The adverse effects of current domestic energy use on households in Nigeria were explored and the need for Government to address those issues that leads to the over-dependence on fuelwood proposed.

REFERENCES

- Adegbemi, B. O., Adegbemi, O. O., Olalekan, A. J., Babatunde, O. O., (2013). Energy consumption and Nigerian economic growth: an empirical analysis. *European Scientific Journal*. 9(4): 25-39. www.ejournal.org/.
- Akinlo, A. E., (2008). Energy consumption and economic growth. *Energy Economics*. 30(5): 2391-2400. www.sciencedirect.com.
- Anierobi, C., Efobi, K., (2013). Waste Pickers and Urban Solid Waste Management System in Nigerian cities: Between Sustainable Policy gap and Survivalist Strategy. *Developing Country Studies*. 3(8): 2013. www.iiste.org
- Abd'razack, N. T. A., Medayese, S. O., Matins, V. I., Idowu, O. O., Adeleye, B. M., Bello, L. O., (2012). An appraisal of household domestic energy consumption in Minna, Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Environmental Science, Toxicology and Food Technology*. 2(3): 16-24. www.iosrjournals.org.
- Akpu, I. V., (2012). Energy Future: The role of impact assessment. IAIA 12 Conference Proceedings, 32nd annual meeting of the international association for impact assessment, May 27-June 1, 2012, Centro de Congresso de Alfândega, Portugal (www.iaia.org).
- Akinbami, J.F.K., Ilori, M.O., Oyebisi, T.O., Akinwumi, I.O., Adeoti, O., (2001). Biogas energy use in Nigeria.- current status, future prospects and policy implications. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. 5, 97-112. www.elsevier.com
- Abayomi, S. O., (2012). Assesment of households' access to electricity and modern cooking fuels in rural and urban Nigeria: Insights from DHS data. *Life Science Journal*. 9(4): 1564-1570. <http://www.lifesciencesite.com>.
- Akpan, G.E., Akpan, U.F., (2012). Electricity Consumption, Carbon Emissions and Economic Growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*. 2(4): 292-306. www.econjournals.com
- Audu, E. B., (2013). Fuel wood consumption and desertification in Nigeria. *International Journal of Science and Technology*. 3(1): 1-5. <http://www.ejournalofsciences.org>.
- Anthony, O. O., Ojochenemi, I. (2012). Econometric analysis of factors influencing fuel wood dememand in rural and peri-urban farm household of Kogi State. *Consilience: The Journal of Sustainable Development*. 8(1): 115-127. <http://consiliencejournal.org/>.

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Anthony, O. O., Emodi, A. I., (2012). Economic analysis of fuelwood production and consumption: evidence from a Nigerian State. *British Journal of Management & Economics*. 2(1): 13-23. www.sciencedomain.org.

Akinwande V.O., Mako A.A., Babayemii, O.J. (2013). Biomass yield, chemical composition and the feed potential of water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*, Mart.Solms-Laubach) in Nigeria. *International Journal of AgriScience*. 3(8): 659-666.
www.inacj.com

Babalola, Y. T., (2010). Awareness and accessibility of environmental information in Nigeria: Evidence from Delta State. *Library Philosophy and Practice 2010*. ISSN 1522-0222.
<http://www.webpages.uidaho.edu/~mbolin/babalola-babalola-okhale.htm>.

Babanyara, Y. Y., Saleh, U. F., (2010). Urbanisation and the choice of fuel wood as a source of energy in Nigeria. *Journal of Human Ecology*. 31(1): 19-26.

Bukola, O. B., (2012). Effects of Unsustainable Use of Biomass for Cooking and Strategies for Their Reduction in Developing Countries. *Developing Country Studies*. 2(3): 19-25. www.iiste.org.

Bolaji, B.O., (2005). The use of sawdust as an alternative source of energy for domestic cooking and a means of reducing deforestation. *Global Journal of Environmental Studies*. 4(1): 73-76.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/gjes.v4i1.2444>

Campbell, C. J., Laherrère, J. H., (1998). The End of Cheap Oil. *Scientific American*. 278(3): 78–83.

Campbell, C., ed. (2000). Feasta Conference 'Money, Energy and Growth. *The imminent peak of global oil production*. Vol. FEASTA review 1. 2000.

Campbell, C.J., (1996). *The Twenty First Century, The World's Endowment of Conventional Oil and its Depletion*. Accessed October 1, 2013 at
<http://www.oilcrisis.com/campbell/camfutur.htm>.

Chikaire, J., Nnadi, F.N., Anyoha, N.O., (2011). Access to sustainable energy: a panacea to rural household poverty in Nigeria. *Continental J. Renewable Energy* 2 (1): 7 – 18. <http://www.wiloludjournal.com>.

Dashehu, B. G., Sambo, A.S., Musa, M., (1992). Comparative performance of sawdust and wood burning stove. *Nigeria Journal of Renewable Energy*, 3(1): 50-55.

Dantama, Y.U., Umar, Y., Abdullah, Y.Z., Nasiru, I. (2012). Energy Consumption - Economic Growth Nexus in Nigeria: An Empirical Assessment Based on ARDL Bound Test Approach. *European Scientific Journal*. 8(12): 141-157;
www.eujournal.org/

Dike, M.C., (1995). Effective Methods of Soil Erosion Control in Farmlands. *Tropical Agriculture*, 202-204

Dzioubinski, O., Chipman, M. (1999): Trend in Consumption and Production: Household Energy Consumption. DESA discussion paper, Number 6.
<http://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/esa99dp6.pdf>.

Edward L. I., Paul E. B., (2013). Assessment of the availability of agricultural residues on a zonal basis for medium- to large-scale bioenergy production in Nigeria. *Biomass and Bioenergy*. 48, 66-74.
www.sciencedirect.com.

Elom, N. I., (2013). Healthcare solid wastes management protocols in Nigeria and implications for human health risk – A review. *Continental J. Environmental Sciences*. 7(1): 11 – 19. <http://www.wiloludjournal.com>.

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- EIA (2011). Country analysis briefs: Nigeria. doi:<http://www.eia.doe.gov/cabs/Nigeria/Background.html>.
- Elijah, I. O., (2012) The benefits and potential impacts of household cooking fuel substitution with bio-ethanol produced from cassava feedstock in Nigeria. *Energy for Sustainable Development*. 16, 352-362. <http://dx.doi.org/j.esd.2012.06.003>.
- Eric, L. H., (1994). Fuel substitution and efficient woodstoves: are they the answers to the fuelwood supply problem in Northern Nigeria. *Environmental Management*. 18(1): 23-32. Springer-Verlag.
- Fawehinmi, A.S. and Oyerinde, O.U., (2002). Household Energy in Nigeria: The challenge of pricing and poverty in fuel switching. *Journal of Energy and Development* 27 (2): 277–284. www.scribd.com/ICEED.
- Famuyide, O. O., Anamayi, S. E., Usman, J.M., (2011). Energy resources' pricing policy and its implications on forestry and environmental implementation in Nigeria. *Continental J. Environmental Sciences*. 2(1): 1-7. <http://www.wiloludjournal.com>.
- Ikporukpo, B. C. O., (1988). Managing oil pollution in Nigeria. In P. O. Sada & F O. Odemerho (Eds.), *Environmental issues and management in Nigerian development* (pp. 224-229). Ibadan, Nigeria: Evans Brothers Ltd.
- Ibidapo-Obe O. and O.O.E. Ajibola (2011). Towards a renewable energy development for rural Power sufficiency. Proceedings of International Conference on Innovations in Engineering and Technology . International Conference on Innovations in Engineering and Technology, University of Lagos, Akoka, Yaba, Lagos, Nigeria. PP. 842-850.
- Lawali, A., Bubuche, T.S., (2013). Correlation analysis of some agronomic traits for biomass improvement in sorghum (*Sorghum Bicolor* L. Moench) genotypes in North-Western Nigeria. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*. 8(28): 5750-3756. DOI:10.5897/AJAR2013.6858
- Ladipo, D. O., Adebisi, A. A., Adewusi, A. G. (2002). Domestic energy and conservation needs for indigenous forest species in Nigeria. *Proceedings of the 28th annual conferences at forestry association of Nigeria*, pp. 240-251.
- Muhiddin A. S., Bintu T. M., Babagana M.T., (2011). A sustainable way for energy in future and challenges for solar energy utilization. *Continental J. Renewable Energy* 2 (1): 26 – 34. <http://www.wiloludjournal.com>.
- MacCarty, N., Still, D., Ogle, D. (2010). Fuel use and emissions performance of fifty cooking stoves in the laboratory and related benchmarks of performance. *Energy for Sustainable Development*, 14(1): 161-71.
- Madubansi, M., Shackleton C.M. (2007) "Changes in fuelwood use and selection following electrification in the Bushbuckridge lowveld, South Africa." *Journal of Environmental Management*, 83,416–426. www.elsevier.com
- Momoh, S., Soaga, J. (1999). Biomass energy consumption in Nigeria: Integrating demand and supply. *Nigerian Journal of Renewable Energy*. 7(1): 78-82.
- Nnaji Barth, (2012). Investment Opportunities in the Nigerian Power Sector. Nigeria Business and Investment Summit, London. July 30, 2012. <http://www.newworldnigeria.com/pdf/HMPPowerSectorReformsPresentation-BoINOCLondon30JULY2012.ppt>.
- Nnaji, C. E., Uzoma, C. C., Chukwu, J. O., (2012). Analysis of factors determining fuelwood use for cooking by rural households in Nsukka area of Enugu State, Nigeria. *Continental J. Environmental Sciences*. 6(2): 1-6. <http://www.wiloludjournal.com>.
- Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (2010) National Petroleum Investment Management Services (NAPIMS) <http://www.nnpcgroup.com/nnpc-group/napims>

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National Bureau of Statistics, NBS 2010. Annual Abstracts of Statistics, Federal Republic of Nigeria. 1 - 611.

Nnaji, C. E., Uzoma, C. C., Chukwu, J. O., (2010). The role of renewable energy resources in poverty alleviation and sustainable development in Nigeria. *Continental J. Social Sciences*. 3, 31-37. <http://www.wiloludjournal.com>.

Nigeria Energy Study Report. Enabling urban poor livelihood policy making: understanding the role of energy services. *Twente Centre for Studies in Technology and Sustainable Development*. Accessed September 30, 2013 at http://www.utwente.nl/mb/cstm/research/urbanenergy/reports/nigeria_rep.doc/.

Nigeria Energy Commission, Report of survey of energy utilisation in the informal sector: A case study of the FCT, Federal Ministry of Power Technical Report. September, 2008.

Nwoke, H. U., (2013). Generation rate of solid waste in Oweri metropolis, Imo State, Nigeria. *Continental J. Environmental Sciences*. 7(1): 8-10. <http://www.wiloludjournal.com>.

NEST (1991). Nigeria's Threatened Environment: A National Profile, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Nwosu, C.A., Nnamdi, M.S., (2013). Relating Electricity Differentials to Nigeria per Capita Income: A Distributed Lag Approach. *International Journal of Business Administration*. 4(3): 86-94. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5430/ijba.v4n3p86>

Omokaro O., (2008). Energy Development in a Fossil Fuel Economy: The Nigerian Experience. The report of a National Dialogue to Promote Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency in Nigeria.

Onyekuru, N. A., Eboh, E. C. (2011). Determinants of Cooking Energy Demand in the Rural Households of Enugu State, Nigeria: An Application of the Bivariate Probit Model. *ASIAN J. EXP. BIOL. SCI.* 2(2): 332-335. <http://www.ajeb.com/vol6/25.pdf>.

Osueke, C.O., Ezeugwu, C.A.K., (2011). Study of Nigeria energy resources and its consumption. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*. 2(1): 1-7. <http://www.ijser.org>.

Olabuisi, I. A, 2011. Domestic energy situation in Nigeria: Technological implications and policy alternatives. *African Technology Policy Network*. ISBN 996-916-62-8.

Ojo, C.O., Chuffor, L., (2013). Accessibility to domestic energy among rural households: case study of Damboa Local Government Area of Borno State, Nigeria. *Greener Journal of Social Sciences*. 3(3): 166-170. www.gjournals.org.

Omaka, O.N., Nwabue, F.I., Itumoh, E.J., Okeke, G.N., (2013). Gas emissions and metallic contents of commonly used fuelwood in Nigeria. *Environment and Pollution*. 2(3): 100-106. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ep.v2n3p100>.

Oyekale, A.S., Dare, A.M., Olugbire, O.O., (2012). Assessment of rural households cooking energy choice during kerosene subsidy in Nigeria: A case study of Oluyole Local Government Area of Oyo State. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*. 7(39): 5405-5411. <http://www.acadaemicjournals.org>.

Olawale, O.E., Ajibola, O. I., Adetokunbo, B. S., (2012). Developing a viable Renewable Energy Policy: A Pathfinder to Millennium Development Goals and Vision 20:2020 . Proceedings of the 13rd Annual International Conference Held at: Mazagan Beach Resort 2400 El Jadida, Casablanca, Morocco. May 15 – 19, 2012.

Odularo, G.O. and Okonkwo, C. (2009). "Does Energy Consumption Contribute to Economic Performance? Empirical Evidence from Nigeria." *Journal of Economics and International Finance*, 1 (2): 044-058

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Olaniyan, K.M.(2010). "Energy consumption and Growth Causality: A Panel Analysis of Five West Africa Countries" paper presented at conference (Abuja, Nigeria). Proceedings of NAEF conference Vol.1, pp. 427-488

Olusegun, O.A. (2008). "Energy consumption and Economic Growth in Nigeria: A Bounds Testing Cointegration Approach." *Journal of Economic Theory*, Vol. 2(4), pp.118-123. <http://ssrn.com/abstract=2156905>

Omotor, D.G. (2008). "Causality between Energy Consumption and Economic Growth in Nigeria." *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences*, Vol. 5 (8), pp. 827 -835. <http://medwelljournals.com/abstract/?doi=pjssci.2008.827.835>

Okoro O.I., Madueme, T.C., (2004). Solar Energy Investments in a Developing Economy, *Renewable Energy*. 29, 1599 - 1610. www.sciencedirect.com

Olatinwo K.B., Adewumi M.O., (2012). Energy Consumption of Rural Farming Households in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa* 14(2): 63-76.

Orhewere, B., Machame, H. (2011). Energy consumption and economic growth in Nigeria. *JORIND*. 9(1): 1596-8308. www.ajol.info/journals/jorind

Ouedraogo, B., (2006). Household Energy Preferences for cooking in Urban Ouagadougou Burkina Faso. *Energy policy* 34, 3787 – 3795. www.sciencedirect.com

Pundo, M. O., Fraser, G. C. G. (2006). Multinomial logit analysis of household cooking fuel choice in rural Kenya: The case of Kisumu district, *Agrekon*, 45(1): 24 -37.

Sambo, A.S., (2010). Renewable energy development in Nigeria. *A Paper Presented at the World Future Council \ 21-strategy Workshop on Renewable Energy, Accra, Ghana, 21-24 June, 2010.*

Shittu, A.M., Idowu, A.O., Otunaiya, A.O., Ismail, A.K., (2004). Demand for energy among households in Ijebu Division, Ogun State, Nigeria. *Agrekon*. 43(1): 38-50.

Twindell, J.W., Weir, A.D. (1986). *Renewable Energy Resources*. Cambridge, University Press.

Taru, V.B., Ndaghu, A.A., Abdullahi, A., Tizhe, J., (2011). Evaluation of fuel wood marketing in Adamawa State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Agriculture: Research and Review*. 3(1): 103-106. <http://www.ecisi.com>

The Cambridge-MIT Institute, (2005). The ImpEEE Project. Assessed October 1, 2013 at <http://www-g.eng.cam.ac.uk/.../DomesticEnergy/.../Domestic%20Energy%20v>

Uzoma, C.C., Nnaji, C.E., Nnaji, M. (2012). The role of energy mix in sustainable development of Nigeria. *Continental J. Social Sciences* 5 (1): 21 – 29. <http://www.wiloludjournal.com>

World Bank, (2006). *Rural energy and development: Improving energy supplies for two billion people*. Washington, DC.

Williams, C. E., (1998). *Reaching the African Female Farmers with Innovative Extension Approaches: Success and Challenges for the future*. Paper Presented at the International Workshop on Women Agricultural Intensification and Household Food Security. University of Cape Coast, Ghana, June 25-28, 1998.

WHO. (2007). *Indoor air pollution: national burden of disease estimates*. World Health Organization Geneva, Switzerland: WHO Press; 2007.

Yemi, K. Nigerian Poverty Profile Report (2012). National Bureau of Statistics. www.nigerianstat.gov.ng.

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Yemi, K. (2013). Economic outlook for the Nigerian economy (2013-2016). National Bureau of Statistics.
www.nigerianstat.gov.ng.

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